

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA):IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Surfactants And Their Role In Pharmaceutical Product Development

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ARTICLE INFO

Received: 11 May 2024

Accepted: 15 May 2024

Published: 21 May 2024

Keywords:

surfactant, Nanotechnology, flexible, amphiphilic.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.11234779

ABSTRACT

Manage the spanned words as you want. Surfactants are an outstanding class of flexible amphiphilic compounds which have a spatially distinct polar hydrophilic head and non-polar hydrophobic tail group. Because of its amphiphilic nature, the precise function of reducing the interfacial tension, the surfactant is broadly utilized in each walk of existence which includes character care products, domestic cleaners, prescription oil recuperation, food handling, and nanotechnologies. This evaluation article will cognize on the class of surfactants, mechanism of movement, antimicrobial features, and particularly emphasize the role of surfactant in pharmaceutical product development. Numerous other realistic software zones which can be tested in terms of foods and gene remedy, biological structures, fitness, and private care products, petroleum and mineral processing are also briefly discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Surfactants are surface active compounds having the potential to lower surface and interfacial tension on the interfaces between gases, beverages, and solids, consequently enabling them to combine or diffuse voluntarily like emulsions in water or other liquids. Large surfactant demand is presently fulfilled via numerous petroleum primarily based chemical surfactants. These compounds are not biodegradable and normally toxic to the environment [1]. Surfactant molecules structurally

include two portions. One portion is hydrophilic in nature and soluble in an aqueous medium, even as the second element is lipophilic, which is soluble in oil however insoluble in an aqueous medium. Structurally these groups are contradictory in directions but their ends are linked to the same molecule, forming an uneven and polar structure. The shape is commonly improved to “determine shape” (Amphiphilic shape) [2]. The molecules of surfactant possess amphiphilic association presenting an allure for both water and oil as

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

indicated in (determine 1). usually, the hydrophilic institution possesses -SO three H, - COOH, and a polyoxyeth-line chain; at the same time as lipophilic institution generally possesses -CF₂-CF, - Si, and a polyoxypropylene chain. In surfactant molecules, the hydrophobicity and lipophilicity adjust with molecular composition and arrangement. for example, when the lipophilic organization is weaker than the hydrophilic, the surfactant becomes water-soluble and it will become oil-soluble surfactant while a lipophilic group is stronger than hydrophilic element. both water-soluble and oil- soluble yields a significant physio-chemical attention of surfactant use. it's far a considerable supply for a realistic surfactant's choice[3]. The surfactants play an active element in the designing and manufacturing of industrial and customer products, comprising cosmetics, detergents, paints, paper merchandise, and prescription drugs[4]. Surfactants are employed too as emulsifiers during the conventional recovery of oil from deeply sited wells of oil[5]. The previous couple of a long time displayed an massive interesting paintings related to the synthesis of surfactants from natural products consisting of sugar-based totally surfactants fatty acids[6-8] and sterols[9]. those surfactants are captivating as they typically are effects biodegraded[10]. compared to standard surfactants, the demand of newly synthesized surfactants having additional houses is increasing at the industrial degree. moreover, a bent to appoint renewable natural products in place of toxic chemical substances along with petrochemicals is also getting extra attention. The new period of world industrialization forces to trade the traditional industries to undertake new growing technology which include biotechnology, which possesses compelling blessings, and additionally offer many research opportunities. In 1980, the arena market of the biotechnology become US \$25 million which immensely grows

to approximately US \$1.7 billion in 1992 and is predicted to increase further than America \$500 billion thru the century quit[11]. especially an inordinate contribution of business chemical substances widely employed in nearly all area of modern industry is mounted by using surfactants. throughout this period, the surfactant call for improved via approximately 300% inside the chemical industry of the us[12]. latest full-size manufacturing surpasses thirty lac tonnes yearly (at a predictable fee folks \$4 billion) and is predicted to amplify over 40 lac tonnes via the cease of the century[13,14]. approximately, fifty four% of the whole surfactants produced are employed in domestic / washing detergents, whilst 32% are handiest designed for commercial packages. Synthetic surfactants, on the whole petroleum-derived, are the maximum abundant commercially available surfactants. although, brief progress in biotechnology and improved ecological attention among customers, joint with the anticipated special rule, has introduced additional stimulus for thoughtful deliberation of organic surfactants as promising substitutes to contemporary yield[1]. The structure of a surfactants

Artificial surfactants and Bio surfactant

Surfactants are amphiphilic molecules having the domain of Both hydrophilic and hydrophobic organizations. The hydrophobic (non-polar) component is commonly a hydrocarbon chain and the polar Element works in various changes mode[15]. Ethylene, propylene oxide, sorbitan esters, ethoxylates, and copolymers are the Most common non-ionic surfactants. Examples of commercially Available ionic surfactants are sulphates (anionic) or ester sulphonates, quaternary ammonium salts (cationic) and fatty acids. Those microbial compounds that mostly show higher floor Vicinity and emulsifying hobby are labelled as bio surfactants. are basically specific compounds which Are prepared mainly

through hydrocarbon-utilizing microorganisms revealing the pastime of the floor. Bio surfactants may Be fashioned using reasonably modest and coffee-value processes and Substrates[16-18].By the usage of organic systems, about different Structural sorts of surfactants are produced, which can't really be produced by way of chemical procedures. These particles can be C498ca6ac814ba2a0e6fddb2ba4d831 to apparel distinctive capabilities by changing the substrate 'Growth or increase settings[19]. Bio surfactants are each biodegradable that is a positive organic function[20-23] and non-poisonous or Less toxic compared to chemical surfactants[24-27]. They ascending soil absolutely marks them ok from a societal and biological point of view.

Classification of surfactants

Anionic surfactants:

The anionic surfactants are liquefied in Water generating the negatively charged surface-lively organization,Whose aqueous answer is neutral or alkaline[28]. Primarily based on the Sort of anionic surfactants, hydrophilic businesses may be categorised Into 5 peptide condensates, particularly: phosphate ester, fatty acid Salt type, sulfate salt type, sulfonate, and carboxylic acid salt Kind. Anionic surfactants are the preliminary and most advanced, and The main class in numerous kinds of surfactants. They will be Broadly employed as foaming retailers, antistatic marketers, dispersants, detergents, emulsifiers, and stabilizers inside the biochemical Features of lifestyles[29]. The structure of anionic surfactant is shown In (determine 2)[30].

Cationic surfactants:

Cationic surfactants are liquefied in water producing advantageous ions of the surface-lively institution. They Possess extremely good superficial movement in an acidic medium and are expected to expose rapid and drop action in an alkaline medium. Based totally on chain association, cationic surfactants are categorized

Into open-chain cationic surfactants, heterocyclic institution cationic Surfactants and bonded intermediate connection cationic surfactants. Cationic surfactants are notably hired for corrosion, rust, breaking, mineral flotation, and sterilization[31].

Non-ionic surfactants:

Nonionic surfactants are not ionized Into any ions in an aqueous medium, and a excessive quantity of oxygen-containing companies form hydrophilic, undertaking Suspension thru hydrogen bonding with water. Normally on-ionic surfactants are existed both in liquid and slurry shape,And their aqueous solubility reduces with temperature elevation.Non-ionic surfactants own wonderful physicochemical features From ionic surfactants due to their fundamental residences. Hydrophilic organizations are labelled into four types like polyhydric, alcohols, polyethylene glycol kind, glycosidic kind, and polyether Type. Non-ionic surfactants are extensively employed in the paper, Textile, food, fiber, plastic, glass, drugs, dyes, insecticides, And lots of other productions. Compared to ionic surfactants,They show notable overall performance; produced in higher amounts After anionic surfactants[

Amphoteric surfactants:

Amphoteric surfactants own each Nice and negative ions. In step with the anion type, amphoteric surfactants may be categorized into lecithin, betaine, imidaz-Oline, and amino acid-type. Amphoteric surfactants have minimal toxicity. It is mild to the pores and skin and possesses extraordinary Biodegradability. Amphoteric surfactants have various makes use of within theNon-public protecting equipment like bathe gel, shampoo, cosmetics,And so forth. And additionally may be employed in industrial softeners and anti-Static marketers.

Speciality surfactants:

Speciality surfactants own diverse Wonderful capabilities, which might be lacking in conventional surfactants, The most critical species is the fluorocarbon surfactant, which has excessive thermal stability, high chemical stability, and super Floor hobby in abundant varieties with a traditional surfactant fantastic element. Consequently, they are normally hired in The fabric, fireplace protection, mineral processing, paper, pesticides,Leather-based, and chemical industries. Moreover, Tin (Sn), Thallium(Ti), and Germanium (Ge) elements also are employed to enhance the molecules of surfactant[34]

Macromolecule surfactants:

normally such surfactants increase To polymeric surfactants whose comparative molecular mass is Higher than 10000, maintaining a floor-lively element. Based totally on Natural assets, they will be categorized into herbal, changed nat-Ural material and composing types[34]. Polymer surfactants may Be implemented as a gelling agent, thickener, emulsifier, fluidity-improving agent, antistatic agent, and dispersing agent. It has been Called a enormous participant of the surfactants intimate. Education of surfactants by using a Fermentation manner Acylpolyols: Acyl polyols synthesized via fermentation are Typically hydroxy fatty acids attached to disaccharides by ester bonds. They are extracellular compounds produced the Actinomycetes like Mycobacterium, Corynebacterium, and Brei-Bacterium[35]. The acyl polyols are found in higher amount in Bacterial cellular walls. Acyl peptide: Acyl peptide (lipopeptides) is commonly recognized As cyclic compounds mounted on a quick peptide chain and hydroxy acid. Bacillus subtilis was used for the production of The maximum searched compound referred to as Surfactant[38,39]. Acyl pep-Tide, as Licensing and Surfactant synthesized via Bacillus Licheniformis, are gifted amphiphiles while it decreases the Floor anxiety, and so on. Surfactin is referred to as one of the rare bio-

Surfactants that have established the industrial utility.It's far reprocessed in distinctive ways to hire for pharmacological functions. The most effective two biosurfactants which give some Controlling evidence are rhamnolipids and Surfactin, and their Molecular genetics has additionally been studied.

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Role of surfactants

Surfactants play a sizable position within the Coaching of different drug transport systems. For the preparation of compounds which are not absolutely soluble in an aqueous Medium, pharmaceutically tolerable surfactants or co-solvents Are classically used to beautify solubility. Polymeric micelles Organized thru surfactants possess a entire set of precise Capabilities that mark them proper favorable carriers of the drug A extensive range of drugs Amid the present day methods to over-Awed such issues, the encapsulation of hydrophobic capsules Into polymeric micelles that includes surfactants are precise Smartest substitutes. A extensive function is played via surfactant Both in pharma and non-pharma area. Comprehensive research Of surfactant inclusion and movement within the

clinical subject would dis-Near a wide type of its capacity in tonic usage. Tapering the Studies on each surfactant might help within the clinical technological know-how's Discipline on the manner to an stronger remedy for numerous complaints.

Preparation of surfactants

Acyl polyols: Acyl polyols synthesized by fermentation are generally hydroxy fatty acids attached to disaccharides by esters bonds. They are extracellular compounds produced through actinomycetes such as Mycobacterium, Corynebacterium and Brei-bacteria[35]. Acyl polyols are present in larger amounts bacterial cell walls.**Glycolipids:** Glycolipids are commonly hydroxy fatty acids linked to a sugar via a glycosidic bond. Sophorolipids and rhamnolipids are clear examples produced through Can-dida and via Pseudomonas, respectively. Rhamnolipids are smart, thanks to which they can be skillfully shaped development in both carbohydrates and carbohydrates sole source of carbon. Considerable attention was paid molecular genetics of rhamnolipids[36]. Sucrose lipid formed through *Serratia marcescens* has recently quarantined and characterized[37]. The yield was has become an excellent emulsifier for the inclusive variety hydrocarbons are petroleum. It was also recommended as surfactant for cleaning oil tanks. **Acyl peptide:** Acyl peptide (lipopeptides) is generally acknowledged as cyclic compounds set up on a quick peptide chain and a hydroxy acid. *Bacillus subtilis* became used for the manufacturing of the maximum searched compound known as Surfactants[.Acyl peptide, as Lichenysin and Surfactin synthesized thru *Bacillus licheniformis*, are gifted amphiphiles while it decreases the surface tension, etc. Surfactin is referred to as one of the uncommon bio-surfactants which have set up the economic utility. The best two biosurfactants which provide some controlling evidence are rhamnolipids and

Surfactin, and their molecular genetics has also been studied.

CONCLUSION

Surfactants are surface-energetic compounds possess the capability of reducing surface and interfacial tension on the interfaces among gases, liquids, and solids and display a important position in The established order and improvement of various pharmaceutical Products through appearing as dispersants, detergents, foaming agents, Wetting marketers and emulsifiers. They've many applications, Including eliminating dirt from garments, pores and skin, and family objects mainly in kitchens and lavatories, they're brought. They Are quite implemented on the enterprise degree. Cationic surfactants Are significantly employed for breaking, corrosion, rust, mineral Floatation and sterilization. The usage of non-ionic surfactants Is appreciably hired in the dyes, fabric, pesticides, paper, Fiber, meals, glass, plastic, drugs, and other industries. Similarly, amphoteric surfactants have diverse makes use of in the individual Shielding equipment like cosmetics, bathe gel, shampoo, and so forth. And Can also be carried out in antistatic agents and business softeners. Besides this, surfactants also carry out antimicrobial features as They forestall the nourishment of numerous pathogenic microbes such Like bacteria, fungi, algae, and virus, etc. and make the pharmaceutical preparations free of dangerous microbes.

REFERENCE

1. Banat, I.M., Makkar, R.S., Cameotra, S.S. Potential commercial applications of microbial surfactants. (2000) *Applied microbiol biotechnol* 53(5): 495-508. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
2. Porter, M.R. *Handbook of Surfactants*. (2013). Pubmed| Crossref| Others
3. Falbe, J. *Surfactants in Consumer Products*. (2012). Pubmed| Crossref| Others

4. Piispanen, P. Synthesis and characterization of surfactants based on natural products. (2002). Pubmed| Crossref| Others
5. Shah, D.O. Surface phenomena in enhanced oil recovery. Other (1981).Pubmed| Crossref| Others
6. Rico-Lattes, I., Lattes, A. Synthesis of new sugar-based surfactants having biological applications: key role of their self-association. (1997) *Colloids and Surfaces A: Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects* 123: 37-48.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
7. Balzer, D. Cloud point phenomena in the phase behavior of alkyl polyglucosides in water. (1993) *Langmuir* 9(12): 3375-3384.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
8. Folmer, B.M., Holmberg, K., Klingskog, E.G., et al. Fatty amide ethoxylates: Synthesis and self-assembly. (2001) *J Surfactants Detergents* 4(2): 175-183.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
9. Folmer, B.M., Svensson, M., Holmberg, K., et al. The physicochemical behavior of phytosterol ethoxylates. (1999) *Journal colloid interface sci* 213(1): 112-120.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
10. Gamia, M., Ribosa, I., Campos, E., et al. Ecological properties of alkylglucosides. (1997) *Chemosphere* 35(3): 545556.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
11. Muller, A., Russell, G., Lucase, P. European Biotech'97. A new economy The Fourth Annual Ernst and Young Report on the European Biotechnology Industry Oxford Business Publishing, Oxford. (1997).Pubmed| Crossref| Others
12. Greek, B.F. Detergent industry ponders products for new decade. (1990) *Chemical & Engineering* 68(5): 37. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
13. Greek, B. Sales of detergents growing despite recession. (1991) *Chemical & Engineering News* 69(4): 25. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
14. Sarney, D.B., Vulfson, E.N. Application of enzymes to the synthesis of surfactants. (1995) *Trends Biotechnol* 13(5): 164-172.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
15. Georgiou, G., Lin, S. C., Sharma, M.M. Surface-active compounds from microorganisms. (1992) *Bio/technology* 10(1): 60.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
16. Kosaric, N. Biosurfactants in industry. (1992) *Pure and Applied Chemistry* 64(11): 1731. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
17. Lang, S., Wullbrandt, D. Rhamnose lipids-biosynthesis, microbial production and application potential. (1999) *Appl Microbiol Biotechnol* 51(1): 22-32. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
18. Makkar, R.S., Cameotra, S.S. Biosurfactant production by microorganisms on unconventional carbon sources. (1999) *J Surfactants Detergents* 2(2): 237-241.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
19. Fiechter, A. Biosurfactants: moving towards industrial application. (1992) *Trends in biotechnology* 10: 208-217. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
20. Zajic, J., Guignard, H., Gerson, D. Emulsifying and surface active agents from *Corynebacterium hydrocarboclastus*. (1977) *Biotechnol bioengineering* 19(9): 1285-1301. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
21. Shoham, Y., Rosenberg, M., Rosenberg, E. Bacterial degradation of emulsan. (1983) *Applied environmental microbial* 46(3): 573-579.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
22. Oberbremer, A., Müller-Hurtig, R., Wagner, F. Effect of the addition of microbial surfactants on hydrocarbon degradation in a soil population in a stirred reactor. (1990)

- Applied Microbiol biotechnology 32(4): 485-489. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
23. Kesting, W., Tummuscheit, M., Schacht, H., et al. Ecological washing of textiles with microbial surfactants. (1996) *Interfaces, Surfactants Colloids Eng* 125-130. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
24. Poremba, K., Gunkel, W., Lang, S., et al. Marine biosurfactants, III. Toxicity testing with marine microorganisms and comparison with synthetic surfactants. (1991) *Zeitschrift für Naturforschung C* 46(3-4): 210-216. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
25. Poremba, K., Gunkel, W., Lang, S., et al. Toxicity testing of synthetic and biogenic surfactants on marine microorganisms. (1991) *Environmental Toxicol Water Qual* 6(2): 157-163. 41. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
26. Van Dyke, M., Lee, H., Trevors, J. T. Applications of microbial surfactants. (1991) *Biotechnol Adv* 9: 241-252. Pubmed| Crossref| Others 42.
27. Flasz, A., Rocha, C., Mosquera, B., et al. A comparative study of the toxicity of a synthetic surfactant and one produced by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 55925. (1998) *Med sci res* 26(3): 181-185. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
28. Schmitt, T.M. Analysis of surfactants. (2001) CRC Press. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
29. Remington, J.P., Gennaro, A.R., Remington: the science and 44. Practice of pharmacy. (1995) Easton, PA: Mack Publishing. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
30. Helenius, A., McCaslin, D., Fries, E., et al. Properties of detergents. (1979) *Methods in enzymology* 56: 734-749. Pubmed| Crossref| Others 45.
31. Kiran, K., Asad, M. Wound healing activity of *Sesamum indicum* L seed and oil in rats. (2008) *Indian J Exp Biol* 46(11): 777-782. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
32. Mishra, M., Muthuprasanna, P., Prabha, K.S., et al. Basics 46. And potential applications of surfactants-a review. (2009). Pubmed| Crossref| Others
33. Zhang, W., Dai, X., Zhao, Y., et al. Comparison of the different types of surfactants for the effect on activity and structure of soybean peroxidase. (2009) *Langmuir*; 25(4): 47. 2363-2368. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
34. uan, C., Xu, Z., Fan, M., et al. Study on characteristics and harm of surfactants. (2014) *J Chemical Pharma Res* 6(7): 2233-2237. 48. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
35. Haferburg, D., Hommel, R., Claus, R., et al. Extracellular microbial lipids as biosurfactants. (1986) *Bioproducts*: 5393. Pubmed| Crossref| Others 49.
36. Sullivan, E.R. Molecular genetics of biosurfactant production. (1998) *Current opinion in biotechnology* 9(3): 263-269. Others Pubmed| Crossref| Others
37. Pruthi, V., Cameotra, S.S. Novel sucrose lipid produced by 50. *Serratia marcescens* and its application in enhanced oil recovery. (2000) *J Surfactants Detergents* 3(4): 533-537. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
38. Kumar, P., Sharma, R., Gajbhiye, A. Characterization of Biosurfactant from *Bacillus* Isolates as Antifungal Agent. 51. (2015) *Indo Global J Pharmaceutical Sci* (2): 117-123. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
39. Sen, R., Swaminathan, T. Application of response-surface methodology to evaluate the optimum environmental conditions for the enhanced production of surfactin. (1997) *Applied Microbiology Biotechnol* 47(4): 358-363. Pubmed| Crossref| Others
40. Han, S., Mallampalli, R.K. The role of surfactant in lung disease and host defense against pulmonary infections. (2015) *Ann Am*

- Thorac Soc 12(5): 765-774.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
41. Morsy, S.M. Role of surfactants in nanotechnology and their applications. (2014) *Int J Curr Microbiol App Sci* 3(5): 237-260.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
42. Prud'homme, R.K. *Foams: Theory: Measurements: Applications.* (1995) Taylor & Francis.Pubmed| Crossref| Others
43. Nayak, A., Dodagatta-Marri, E., Tsolaki, A.G., et al. An insight into the diverse roles of surfactant proteins, SP-A and SP-D in innate and adaptive immunity. (2012) *Front immunol* 3: 131. Pubmed| Crossref| Others.

HOW TO CITE: Disha P. Wankhede, Damini A. Mundhare, Laxmi S. Deshmukh, Nandakishor B. Deshmukh, Swati P. Deshmukh, *Surfactants And Their Role In Pharmaceutical Product Development*, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2024, Vol 2, Issue 5, 1076-1083. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11234779>